

Advantages of Ceramic Inlays Over Fillings in the Restoration of Damaged Molars

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Abstract: The restoration of defects in the hard tissues of teeth remains one of the most pressing problems in modern dentistry. The use of composite restorations on load-bearing occlusal surfaces is limited due to the relatively low physical-mechanical properties of these materials (Radlinsky S.V., 1996, 1997; Fusayama T., 1990; Liebenberg W.H., 1996).

An effective restoration method is the use of biocompatible and aesthetic ceramic inlays to restore molar teeth (Arutyunov S.D., 1997; Holand W., 1998; Leinsinger M., 1998; Ubassi G., 2000).

Inlays and onlays not only serve as an alternative to metal-ceramic crowns but also restore the chewing function of the tooth by affecting the flexibility of cusps and the material's compliance, which are key parameters in the tooth-restoration complex (Douglas W.H., 1996; Dietschi, D., 1997).

Keywords: indirect restoration; ceramic onlay; tooth anatomy and aesthetics; large cavities, multiple caries, stressed-deformed state.

Relevance of the Problem

One of the relevant issues in orthopedic dentistry is the restoration of complete crown defects in teeth. According to a number of researchers, such pathology occurs quite frequently, accounting for up to 16.7% of cases [3,4,5].

Pathologies of tooth hard tissues remain an important problem in dental practice today. Caries and its complications are currently among the most common dental diseases [1,14].

Restoring small defects in a tooth crown typically does not pose significant difficulty for the dentist. However, more complex clinical situations arise with completely destroyed tooth crowns, especially when combined with a low clinical crown [17].

According to several researchers, this pathology occurs fairly often, ranging from 12 to 16.7% of cases [18,19,22]. The main difficulty lies in the fact that a low clinical crown (the core part of the inlay) cannot provide sufficient retention for a non-removable prosthetic structure [2].

Analysis of long-term outcomes in such clinical situations shows that loss of fixation in non-removable prosthetic structures occurs in 38% of cases [5].

**Despite significant advancements in the fabrication of various restorations, the number

of complications following the restoration of hard dental tissues remains quite high. This is primarily related to the adhesion to the hard tissues of the tooth, the biocompatibility of the bonding materials and the restorations, which undoubtedly leads to frequent debonding of inlays. Long-term results of prosthetic treatment in such clinical situations show that retention failure in non-removable prosthetic structures occurs in up to 38% of cases, while ceramic fractures occur in up to 15% of cases [24,26,28].

Objective of the Study: To evaluate the effectiveness of ceramic inlays in the treatment of patients with multiple carious lesions.

Materials and Methods: For the purposes of this study, 25 patients with 115 ceramic inlays placed on posterior teeth were examined. These inlays had been fabricated by dentists at the Tashkent State Dental Institute's dental clinic 3-5 years ago using the Impress technology for the treatment of multiple caries. This group is referred to as the "CI group" (ceramic inlays). Additionally, 25 patients with 218 composite resin fillings replacing defects in the posterior teeth were examined. The maximum period since the last restoration of molar and premolar defects was 5 years, and the minimum was 2 years. These patients formed the "CF group" (composite fillings).

Analysis of the patients' stomatognathic systems with multiple caries, where defects in posterior teeth were restored with light-cured composite fillings, revealed a higher incidence of gingivitis and periodontitis compared to those with ceramic inlays in their posterior teeth. Specifically, the prevalence of gingivitis (K05.1) and periodontitis (K05.3) in the CF group 3-5 years after placement of the fillings was 52.0% (13 people) and 16.0% (4 people), respectively, while in the CI group, these figures were 32.0% (8 people) and 12.0% (3 people) (Table 1).

The prevalence of increased tooth wear (K03.0) was also higher among those with composite fillings—10.0% (21 people) compared to 2.9% (2 people) among those with ceramic inlays in their posterior teeth.

Both groups of patients had an acceptable level of oral hygiene according to the IGH-U index, but the hygiene level was worse in the composite filling group: 2.7 ± 0.2 compared to 2.4 ± 0.2 in the ceramic inlay group.

As shown, the dental status of patients with multiple composite fillings in posterior teeth over long-term follow-up is characterized by more negative outcomes compared to patients with ceramic inlays. Key indicators such as the prevalence of periodontal diseases (68.0% vs. 44.0%) suggest this difference.

- ✓ Prevalence of increased tooth wear (16.0% and 4.0%),
- ✓ Caries intensity according to the DMFT index (12.4 and 10.6); the **C component** in the DMFT index (1.5 and 0.3);
- ✓ Intensity of periodontal diseases according to the CPI index (2.6 and 1.9).

Dependence of the prevalence of periodontal diseases and increased tooth wear on the presence of composite resin fillings and ceramic inlays in posterior teeth

This difference can be explained not only by the lower physical-chemical properties of composite materials, which are subject to biodegradation, microbial colonization, and wear, but also by the use of composite materials in cases of significant destruction of the occlusal surface of posterior teeth beyond the limits, where the effectiveness of composites is reduced to no more than 50.0% of the occlusal surface. In this study, 56.3% of composite fillings in posterior teeth with multiple caries replaced defects of class II according to Black, with occlusal surface destruction greater than 50.0% in 28.0% of cases. 16.7% of the fillings had a mesio-occluso-distal location. 40.7% of the teeth under composite fillings were devitalized.

It was found that ceramic inlays are used with more caution. For example, 37.1% of the inlays replaced class II defects, with occlusal surface destruction in 14.5%, mesio-occluso-distal location in 56.9%, and in devitalized teeth in 37.1%. Inlays are more commonly used to restore class I defects in devitalized teeth with more than 50.0% occlusal surface destruction.

The functional study conducted demonstrates the greater feasibility of using ceramic inlays for restoring multiple carious lesions in posterior teeth, as they prevent occlusal-articulatory disorders and dysfunction of the masticatory apparatus.

Disorders typical for patients with multiple caries when replacing defects in posterior teeth with composite resin fillings over the long term. In the context of a large number of composite fillings, the presence of intact antagonistic teeth reduces but does not eliminate the occurrence of masticatory dysfunction. During the clinical examination of the stomatognathic system, all patients with multiple composite fillings exhibited a decrease in the height of the lower third of the face by 1-4 mm, and to a lesser extent (1-2 mm) when intact antagonistic teeth were present in the posterior dental arches.

The clinical analysis of occlusion, supplemented by the analysis of occlusion on diagnostic models, showed:

- The presence of wear facets in the frontal and posterior sections of the dental arches, including on the composite resin fillings themselves, in all patients in the CF group.
- Significant variability in the location of occlusal contact points on the occlusal surface of posterior teeth restored with composite material.

Analysis of the quality of composite resin fillings and ceramic inlays with a service life of 3-5 years, placed in posterior teeth with multiple caries, demonstrated the undeniable advantages of ceramic inlays.

This data shows a significant difference in quality, where ceramic inlays consistently performed better in terms of anatomical form, color match, and marginal adaptation, especially when compared to composite resin fillings. Composite fillings, on the other hand, demonstrated higher failure rates in these areas, underscoring the long-term benefits of using ceramic materials for restorations in posterior teeth with multiple caries.

(absence of a visible gap at the margin, no probe entrapment); 34.8% (76 fillings) of composite resin fillings received a Bravo rating, while 15.7% of ceramic inlays (18 inlays) exhibited a visible gap at the margin with probe entrapment; 17.4% of composite fillings (38 fillings) and 4.3% of ceramic inlays (5 inlays) showed wear or fractures with exposure of the dentin (Charlie rating); 9.6% of composite fillings (21 fillings) and 6.1% of ceramic inlays (7 inlays) were missing completely or were largely absent (Delta rating)

Anatomical Form Criterion: Composite resin fillings were classified as Alfa (filling material continues the existing anatomical form), Bravo (filling material does not continue the existing anatomical form), Charlie (significant loss of filling material with exposure of dentin) in the following proportions: Alfa 48.6% (106 fillings), Bravo 37.6% (82 fillings), and Charlie 13.3% (29 fillings). For ceramic inlays, the corresponding proportions were: Alfa 92.2% (106 inlays), Bravo 1.7% (2 inlays), and Charlie 6.1% (7 inlays).

Caries Criterion: The Alfa and Bravo evaluations (respectively, probe entrapment at the edge of the filling combined with softening, pigmentation, demineralization of tooth tissue, or the absence of such signs) were as follows for composite resin fillings: Alfa 76.6% (167 fillings) and Bravo 23.4% (51 fillings). For ceramic inlays, Alfa received 88.7% (102 inlays) and Bravo 11.3% (13 inlays).

Color Match Criterion: Composite resin fillings were classified as Alfa, Bravo, and Charlie in the following proportions: Alfa 32.1% (70 fillings), Bravo 52.3% (114 fillings), and Charlie

15.6% (34 fillings), reflecting whether the color, shade, and light translucency matched the adjacent tooth structures (Alfa and Bravo) or were outside the normal color range of the tooth (Charlie). For ceramic inlays, the respective evaluations were Alfa 90.4% (104 inlays), Bravo 3.5% (4 inlays), and Charlie 6.1% (7 inlays).

Color of Cavity Margins Criterion: The Alfa criterion (absence of color change at the margin between the filling and adjacent tooth structures) was observed in 58.6% of composite resin fillings (127 fillings), while Bravo (color change at the margin) was observed in 29.5% (65 fillings), and Charlie (spread of color change along the margin towards the pulp) in 11.9% (26 fillings). For ceramic inlays, the respective proportions for Alfa, Bravo, and Charlie were 82.4% (262 inlays), 7.6% (24 inlays), and 10.1% (32 inlays). Summary of Evaluations:

Based on the aggregate quality evaluations of composite resin fillings and ceramic inlays according to specific criteria, the overall assessments were as follows:

- ****Romeo (Excellent)**:** 29.8% of composite fillings (65 fillings) and 73.9% of ceramic inlays (85 inlays).
- ****Sierra (Acceptable):** 29.8% of composite fillings (65 fillings) and 10.4% of ceramic inlays (12 inlays).
- ****Tango (Unacceptable, requiring preventive replacement or correction):** 17.4% of composite fillings (38 fillings) and 4.3% of ceramic inlays (5 inlays).

******(In the category requiring immediate replacement, the cavities from which the fillings or inlays have fallen out)/

The conducted analysis confirms the vulnerability of composite resin fillings compared to ceramic inlays when replacing multiple defects in the posterior teeth. In similar clinical conditions, the superior physical-mechanical properties and biocompatibility of ceramics become evident.

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